

Hypergeometric ${}_0F_3$ functions and the Fourier Transform of κ -exponentials

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Abstract – Here we show that the Fourier transform of the κ -exponential Kaniadakis functions is generating time correlation functions based on the hypergeometric ${}_0F_3$ functions.

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The κ -exponential functions have been determined by G. Kaniadakis in the framework of his generalized statistics (see Kaniadakis, 2013). The κ -exponential has expression: $exp_\kappa(u) = [\sqrt{1 + \kappa^2 u^2} + \kappa u]^{1/\kappa}$. The function has been used for comparison to q-Gaussian Tsallis function in fitting Raman spectral lines (Sparavigna, 2023). In analogy, we used a κ -Gaussian function with $u = -\beta(x - x_o)^2$:

$$exp_\kappa(u) = \left[\sqrt{1 + \kappa^2 \beta^2 (x - x_o)^4} - \kappa \beta (x - x_o)^2 \right]^{1/\kappa} \quad (1)$$

Here we will consider (1) in the following form, with dimensionless variable w about $w_o = 0$:

$$\kappa\text{-Gaussian} = \left[\sqrt{1 + \kappa^2 w^4} - \kappa w^2 \right]^{1/\kappa} \quad (2)$$

κ is ranging from 0 to 1.

Let us investigate the Fourier transform of (2), to find a possible time correlation function related to fitted Raman bands. As previously made for q-Gaussians (Sparavigna, 2023), let us use WolframAlpha software for function:

$$\left[\sqrt{1 + w^4} - w^2 \right]^{1/\kappa}$$

Of course, we can obtain the final transform considering the scaling κw^2 into $t/\sqrt{\kappa}$. For instance:

$$\mathcal{F}_w[(1 + w^2)^{-1/2}](t) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} K_0(t \operatorname{sgn}(t)) \quad \mathcal{F}_w[(1 + A^2 w^2)^{-1/2}](t) = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} K_0\left(\frac{|t|}{\sqrt{A^2}}\right)}{\sqrt{A^2}}$$

WolframAlpha does not provide a result for a generic index κ of the exponential, So let us provide the results for some values of it.

$$\kappa = 0.1$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}_w \left[\sqrt[0.1]{\sqrt{1+w^4} - w^2} \right] (t) = & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \left(2.52206 \times 10^{-20} |t|^{19} {}_0F_3 \left(; 5.25, 5.75, 11; -\frac{t^4}{256} \right) + \right. \\ & 0.562253 {}_0F_3 \left(; -3.75, \frac{1}{2}, 6.25; -\frac{t^4}{256} \right) - \\ & \left. 0.0143261 t^2 {}_0F_3 \left(; -3.25, \frac{3}{2}, 6.75; -\frac{t^4}{256} \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\kappa = 0.25$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}_w \left[\sqrt[0.25]{\sqrt{1+w^4} - w^2} \right] (t) = & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \left(0.0000389582 |t|^7 {}_0F_3 \left(; 2.25, 2.75, 5; -\frac{t^4}{256} \right) + \right. \\ & 0.903694 {}_0F_3 \left(; -0.75, \frac{1}{2}, 3.25; -\frac{t^4}{256} \right) - \\ & \left. 0.0642104 t^2 {}_0F_3 \left(; -0.25, \frac{3}{2}, 3.75; -\frac{t^4}{256} \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\kappa = 0.5$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}_w \left[\sqrt[0.5]{\sqrt{1+w^4} - w^2} \right] (t) = & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \left(0.1309 |t|^3 {}_0F_3 \left(; 1.25, 1.75, 3; -\frac{t^4}{256} \right) + 1.35554 {}_0F_3 \left(; 0.25, \frac{1}{2}, 2.25; -\frac{t^4}{256} \right) - \right. \\ & \left. 0.353157 t^2 {}_0F_3 \left(; 0.75, \frac{3}{2}, 2.75; -\frac{t^4}{256} \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\kappa = 0.75$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}_w \left[\sqrt[0.75]{\sqrt{1+w^4} - w^2} \right] (t) = & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \left(-1.65727 |t|^{1.66667} {}_0F_3 \left(; 0.916667, 1.41667, 2.33333; -\frac{t^4}{256} \right) + \right. \\ & 1.83722 {}_0F_3 \left(; 0.583333, \frac{1}{2}, 1.91667; -\frac{t^4}{256} \right) + \\ & \left. 1.05342 t^2 {}_0F_3 \left(; 1.08333, \frac{3}{2}, 2.41667; -\frac{t^4}{256} \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\kappa = 0.99$$

$$\mathcal{F}_w \left[{}^{0.99} \sqrt{\sqrt{1+w^4} - w^2} \right] (t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \left(-1.54715 |t|^{1.0202} {}_0F_3 \left(; 0.755051, 1.25505, 2.0101; -\frac{t^4}{256} \right) + \right. \\ \left. 2.44177 {}_0F_3 \left(; 0.744949, \frac{1}{2}, 1.75505; -\frac{t^4}{256} \right) + \right. \\ \left. 0.346461 t^2 {}_0F_3 \left(; 1.24495, \frac{3}{2}, 2.25505; -\frac{t^4}{256} \right) \right)$$

We have function ${}_0F_3$. This is a Hypergeometric function that we can find defined at https://specialfunctions.wiki.org/index.php/Hypergeometric_0F3 as:

$${}_0F_3(; b_1, b_2, b_3; z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(b_1)_k (b_2)_k (b_3)_k} \frac{z^k}{k!},$$

$(b_i)_k$ denotes a Pochhammer symbol: $(b)_k = \frac{\Gamma(b+k)}{\Gamma(b)}$.

References

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